

Reaction Mechanism of the Oxygen Evolution on
Ru and RuO₂ electrodes – a soft X-ray Absorption
Spectroscopy approach

Supporting Information

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Figure S1a Time course of the raw $\Delta\mu$ signals at 531, 533 and 529 eV along with that of the applied potential recorded during cyclic polarization of RuO_2 electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 at 5 mV/s. A smoothed signal is marked in red.

Figure S1b Time course of the potential and of the raw $\Delta\mu$ signals at 531, 533, 534 and 529 eV along with that of the applied potential recorded during cyclic polarization of Ru electrode in 0.1 M HClO₄ at 5 mV/sA smoothed signals are marked in red.

Figure S2a Time derivatives of the $\Delta\mu$ signals located at 531 eV (black), 533 eV (red) and 529 eV (blue) recorded during cyclic polarization of RuO₂ electrode in 0.1 M HClO₄ at 5 mV/s. The lower pane shows the time course of electrode potential.

Figure S2b Time derivatives of the $\Delta\mu$ signals located at 531 eV (black), 533 eV (red) and 529 eV (blue) recorded during 1st cycle of Ru electrode polarization in 0.1 M HClO₄ at 5 mV/s. The lower pane shows the time course of electrode potential.

Figure S2c Time derivatives of the $\Delta\mu$ signals located at 531 eV (black), 533 eV (red) and 529 eV (blue) recorded during 4th cycle of Ru electrode polarization in 0.1 M HClO₄ at 5 mV/s. The lower pane shows the time course of electrode potential.